

Challenges To Revitalizing Indian Agriculture

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Abstract

One of the challenges for achieving inclusive growth during the 11th Plan and beyond relates to the revival of Indian agriculture. The farm population has been waiting patiently year after year for a 'new deal' for agriculture. Doubling agricultural growth to 4% is the immediate challenge. 'Going by the package' in the recent budget, the approach seems to be incremental, rather than a holistic strategy for reviving agriculture. The finance minister claimed that earlier budgets concentrated on economic growth and we would now concentrate on inclusiveness. The damage has already been done by neglecting some of the 'inclusive' sectors like agriculture. It is important to stress that growth and equity should be pursued simultaneously rather than following 'growth first and equity next' approach. It concluded that the Indian agriculture sectors contribute optimally to the economic growth of the country and eventually the well-being and prosperity of the farming community.

Keywords: Traditional crops, problems- solutions,

Introduction

The agriculture sector has many problems. Its growth rate was less than 2% in the last decade. Yield growth has also declined. Farmers' suicides have continued, increased in some States. Farming is becoming a non-viable activity. Further scope for increase in net sown area is limited. Land degradation in the form of depletion of soil fertility, erosion and water logging has increased. There has been a decline in the surface irrigation expansion rate and a fall in the ground water table. Disparities in productivity across regions and crops have persisted. The supply and demand side constraints have to be removed to raise growth. The support systems have to be tuned to improve productivity and incomes of farmers with emphasis on small and marginal farmers and dry-land areas.

Trade liberalisation has also raised the risk and uncertainty. The policies have to keep in mind the increasing risk in agriculture. Agriculture policies have to be gender sensitive too since the share of women is increasing. Cost reduction in agriculture is important to compete in the globalised world. Crop sector may not be able to grow at 4% per annum. But horticulture and allied activities like dairying, poultry and fisheries have to grow at the rate 6 to 7% to achieve 4% growth in agriculture. The most important problem for the farmers is output price fluctuations. There is a big gap between producer prices and consumer price.

Agriculture, the backbone of Indian economy, contributes to the overall economic growth of the country and determines the standard of life for more than 50% of the Indian population. Agriculture contributes only about 14% to the overall GDP but its impact is felt in the manufacturing sector as well as the services sector as the rural population has become a significant

consumer of goods and services in the last couple of decades. The situation in Indian Agriculture, and particularly farmer distress, is increasingly getting the focus Problems faced by the Agriculture Sector.

Fragmented Land Holding

Nearly 80% of the 140 million farming families hold less than 2 acres of land. Large land holdings enable the farmer to implement modern agricultural techniques and boost productivity. Small land holdings restrict the farmer to use traditional methods of farming and limit productivity. As land holdings are small, more people invariably work on the farms in the rural areas and coupled with the obsolete technology, farm incomes come down.

Irrigation Problems

Most of the farming in India is monsoon dependent – if monsoons are good, the entire economy (and not just the agricultural sector) is upbeat and when the monsoon fails, everyone everywhere takes a hit to some extent. The problem here is of proper management of water or the lack of it. Irrigation which consumes more than 80% of the total water use in the country needs a proper overhaul if the country has to improve agricultural output and boost the overall economy.

Seed Problems

Most of the farmers – especially the poor and marginal ones – are dependent on seeds sold in the market. Moreover, the HYV seeds as well as the GM seeds which promise higher yields force the farmers to buy seeds for every crop. With spurious seeds hitting the market, the farmers' woes have exceeded all limits. Sometimes seeds do not give the stated/claimed yields and farmers run into economic troubles. In many cases of GM and HYV seeds, farmers are forced to use high amounts of fertilisers and pesticides, provide large amounts of water

(irrigation) and abide to all the other farming requirements that the companies mandate to get the proper yields. A proper regulation/legislation to hold seed companies accountable for false claims is the need of the hour as companies use legal loopholes to push the blame on to the farmers in the case of failed crops.

Over Dependence On Traditional Crops

Every crop requires certain climatic conditions to give the best yields. Though rice and wheat are produced in a large area in India, certain areas can readily switch to other crops to get better productivity. India is importing cooking oil from abroad though we have the necessary conditions to grow more oilseeds here. Heavy dependence on traditional rice and wheat points to the lack of a proper national plan on agriculture. Excess stocks in a few crops lead to problems in the selling of the produce, storage and shortage of other essential farm output. Moreover, if the farm output is skewed towards crops like rice, irrigation and ground water facilities are misused by farmers, which lead to a host of other problems.

Supply Channel Bottlenecks And Lack Of Market Understanding

Supply channel bottlenecks and lack of a proper marketing channel are serious problems for a farmer who is already burdened with a host of troubles. These are issues which need to be tackled at the regional, state and national levels. Lack of a proper marketing channel forces the farmers to distress sale, makes them victims in the hands of greedy middlemen and ultimately restricts their income. An improper marketing and storage channel also leads to storage problems in the years where productivity is good, leads to poor agricultural exports due to problems in maintaining quality and in many cases leads to gross wastage of valuable food grains and other farm output. Food wastage running into thousands of crores of rupees every year is nothing short of a crime in a country where more than 25% is below poverty line and where millions go hungry day after day. Lack of a national strategy in terms of agricultural production leads to production of some crops exceeding the requirement and to some crops well below the minimum limits.

Government Handling Of The Issue

MSP, overall agricultural strategy of the country, PDS, storage/granaries, lack of export market creation. India lacks the required number of storage facilities (granaries, warehouses, cold storage etc) which negates the advantage of having a bumper crop in years of good monsoon. Exports in agricultural sector are also not very encouraging with a share of just 10% of the total exports, for a country where more than 50% of population is dependent on agriculture. The **Minimum Support Prices (MSP)** offered by the Government is a

double edged sword – MSPs protect farmers from being exploited by middlemen but during times of excess crop, Government runs the risk of an unnecessary fiscal deficit by buying the excess produce. Lack of proper storage facilities and lack of a proper international market linkage leads to lower exports and in many cases leads to huge amount of wastage.

There is basically six factors need attention in the short and medium terms. These are: (a) infrastructure; (b) land and water management; (c) research and extension; (d) inputs including credit; (e) marketing including price policy; and (f) diversification and development of rural non-farm sector. Institutions have to be developed in all these areas. Investment in irrigation and rural infrastructure is important for agricultural growth. It is known that public investment in agriculture is lower than the requirements needed for achieving 4% growth. Bharat Nirman Programme is in the right direction but the progress has to be much faster.

The decline in productivity growth is attributed, among other things, to the deterioration in soil quality and water shortages including ground water depletion. Therefore, land and water management should be given the number one priority. Investment in irrigation, watershed development and, water conservation by the community are needed under water management. The pros and cons of the government's recent proposal of direct delivery of fertilisers to farmers are not known now. In order to improve soil quality, the government can restructure the fertiliser subsidies in such way that it would reduce the consumption of nitrogenous and encourage phosphatic and potassic fertilisers.

As the national commission on farmers mentions, there is a knowledge gap in the existing technology. So extension becomes crucial for improving agricultural productivity. In view of the high variability in agro-climatic conditions, particularly in unfavorable areas, research has to become increasingly location-specific. True, there have been some improvements in the flow of farm credit in recent years. The government is insensitive to the four distributional aspects of agricultural credit. These are: (a) not much improvement in the share of small and marginal farmers; (b) decline in credit-deposit (CD) ratios of rural and semi-urban branches; (c) increase in the share of indirect credit in total agricultural credit; and (d) significant regional inequalities in credit.

Agriculture is highly influenced by climate and weather conditions. Every single decision in agriculture is dependent on weather conditions. Farmers are at huge risk due to the extreme weather conditions as an impact of climate change leading to

unseasonal rains and drought. This condition is worsened as our farmers are not prepared with new adaptation and mitigation strategies. This can be solved by adopting climate specific strategies for different demographic regions. A large number of farmers in India are marginal farmers and they still prefer non organized sector for their credit needs. The reason is complex documentation process done by banks. It is important to popularise cooperative farming and create awareness among the farmers for availing loan facility from organized sector. Banks should provide hassle free loan facility to the farmers. Government has come up with several schemes and subsidies for the farmers but they do not reach to all small and marginal farmers. There should be effective implementation and proper follow up and evaluation of these schemes in order to ensure that it reaches to each and every farmer.

Solutions

1. Consolidation of village lands and cooperative farming will ease the burden of **fragmented land** holdings. When the farmers form a consortium at the village level, the aggregate land can be farmed by using the latest technology. Banks too will be willing to lend money to a village consortium which can be utilised to boost farm productivity, employ sustainable farming methods, reduce over – dependence on fertilisers and thus solve many problems.
2. The overall risk of a crop failure is less in this case and small farmers have a higher chance of earning a decent income at the end of the harvest season. Agricultural intensity also rises when a planned strategy adopted at the village level is implemented.
3. Agricultural credit and farm mechanisation for small and marginal farmers will continue to be difficult unless pooling of farm resources and/or a joint usage of farm technology are employed.

Irrigation problems can be addressed by Government – preferably at the State and National levels. Though the Government cannot force farmers to produce only the designated crops in particular areas, it can surely educate them about the alternatives.

1. When proper techniques (in water management at the regional, state and national levels as well as a crop plan of what to produce and where to produce) are employed, it will be a win – win situation for both the farmers as well as the country.
2. Irrigation problems as well as problems due to single/traditional crop dependence can be solved by a national level plan for agricultural production. Government can encourage farmers to shift to cash crops (oil seeds etc) instead of food crops in areas where food crops are not at

an advantage to reduce imports and also to boost exports.

Seed problems can be overcome by creating in house seed banks at the village level for traditional crops (thereby reducing farmer dependence on external seed banks), selling Government approved seeds through proper channels (to eradicate spurious seeds) and strict penalties on seed marketing companies in case the seeds do not match the claims – germination and yield - of the companies. Terminator seeds should not be encouraged as a matter of principle as they force farmers to buy seeds for every crop.

1. Scientific research in this subject is to be encouraged to promote seeds which are mild on resource requirements but help the farmers in boosting the yields.
2. Sometimes small innovations at the grass root levels can solve a host of problems specific to a particular region. District agricultural officers must make it a habit to encourage such ideas and also take part in knowledge sharing to implement the ideas at a regional level.
3. Some **sustainability** solutions are proper crop management on the basis of water availability, crop rotation, deploying modern agricultural practices to boost productivity, switching over to organic farming (village pools will reduce costs), thrust on allied activities.
4. For organic farming, first of all, a proper awareness has to be built – among both the farmers as well as consumers. **Organic farming** reduces the unnecessary usage of artificial fertilisers, reduces water consumption, strikes a good balance between the local environment and the farm output, helps the land retain its fertility for a long time, reduces costs in the long run and also with the creation of a proper market in the towns and cities establishes a virtuous cycle between consumers and farmers.

Storage facilities can be boosted by small cold storage or granaries at village level which can be established from Panchayat funds and loans to the village society (this eliminates dumping of excess crops in the market yard).

1. At the **National level** an **agricultural strategy or policy** to improve information exchange, national level cold storage chains and logistic network (If Walmart can do, then Government of India can also do!) is the need of the hour. Proper management of **PDS** has to be done to cut down wastes so that a reliable estimate of the food grain needs will be made. The excess (after keeping reserves for a potential drought year) can be exported provided the quality is maintained by means of proper storage.

2. Food wastage can thus be cut down and agricultural trade balance can be improved if there is a national level plan.

Improving supply chain and processing capacities: Massive post-harvest losses due to lack of adequate cold chain and storage infrastructure and processing capacity impact farmer income adversely. The private sector must be allowed to procure, store and distribute grains, can start with the Public Distribution System. This will bring down the cost for the Government by 25 per cent and result in storage capacities being set up in consuming States.

1. In the case of perishables, increased processing capacity can ensure price stability and protect farmer interests. Introduction of new technologies can help in extending the shelf life of fruits and vegetables. 100-per cent FDI in food retailing including e-commerce, introduced last year, will help strengthen investment in front-end retail, which ultimately works in favour of farmers.
2. There is a need to introduce modern entrepreneurship to Indian agriculture. Promoting agricultural services under the Start-up India Scheme will help bring modern technology and inputs to farmers.

Conclusion

The Government's intent is progressive it talks about programmes such as 'More Crop per Drop', 'Pradhan Mantra Fasal Bima Yojna', 'Direct benefit transfer to farmers. Yet, to double farmers' income, we will have to make agriculture a viable business opportunity and governments should focus more on enablers rather than hand-outs and retrospective incentives. The Indian agriculture sectors contribute optimally to the economic growth of the country and eventually the well-being and prosperity of the farming community.

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